

Review

Impact of Hot Spot on P-V Characteristics and Maximum Power Point Tracker Strategy: An in-depth Review

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Abstract: Photovoltaic technology is receiving increasing attention due to its abundant nature, inexhaustible, easy to implement with low maintenance cost, whose use will reach 940 GW in 2021. The non-participation of mechanical or mobile components within it makes it still efficient and increasingly attractive. Faced with this dizzying growth, the health of photovoltaic modules must be a concern, as various failures can occur, of which nearly 50% of defects are hot spots. These faults can lead to changes in PV characteristics, and therefore maximum voltage. This can also change the maximum power available to the load and thus reduce the efficiency of photovoltaic energy production. In order to solve this problem that lies in minimizing these impacts, we review the hot spot fault, its equivalent model, and the operation and strategy of the maximum power point tracker in this specific case. Finally, it is clearly established that photovoltaic systems are extremely sensitive to the hot-spot fault, the use of a MPPT maximum power point tracker is an undeniable solution for improving the efficiency of photovoltaic systems.

Keywords: PV system; Hot Spot; I(V) and P(V) Characteristics; Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT).

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Introduction

The requirement to use low-carbon power plants is encouraging the increased use of renewable energy sources such as geothermal, photovoltaic (PV), biomass, tidal and wind power. Among these sources, solar photovoltaic energy is increasingly appreciated because of its abundant and inexhaustible nature, in addition to its great flexibility of installation as well as its low maintenance cost. In addition, the non-participation of mechanical or mobile components in it also makes it more efficient compared to other renewable sources. The use of photovoltaic systems is well identified and widely applied in current technologies, such as, alternative energy obstetrics, solar vehicle construction, battery charging, water pumping, satellite network, etc., where the photovoltaic module being the basic essential component in this photovoltaic system that, allows to transform solar energy into electrical energy [1]. Until 2021, the worldwide use of photovoltaic energy has reached 940 GW [2], as a consequence of the global socio-economic growth. With this unending meteoric rise as well as the increasing use of this solar energy, the health of photovoltaic modules must be a

concern because during operation, these modules can suffer various failures with nearly 50% of the defects being hot spots [3]. Given the importance of the health of photovoltaic modules and the concern to ensure the production efficiency of photovoltaic systems, while maximizing its power output in particular, this article reviews the so-called hot spot fault, its mode of operation and detection as well as the strategy of monitoring the maximum power point that can prove essential in the search for the performance of the photovoltaic system as well as the safety of people and property.

1. I-V characteristics of a photovoltaic cell

Under a given illumination, any photovoltaic (PV) cell is characterized by current-voltage (I-V) and power-voltage (P-V) curves, as shown in Figure 2 [4], which represents the set of electrical configurations that this cell can take. However, the equations needed to represent these I-V characteristics, based on the equivalent model to a diode as shown in Figure 1, are [5-6]:

$$I_{pv} = I_{ph} - I_D - I_p \tag{1}$$

With the photoelectric current I_{ph} which is expressed as,

$$I_{ph} = [I_{sc} + k_i(T - 298)] \frac{G}{G_0} \tag{2}$$

The diode current I_D is expressed as,

$$I_D = I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V_{pv} + R_s I_{pv}}{V_t a}\right) - 1 \right] \tag{3}$$

Where V_t is the junction thermal voltage and

$$V_t = \frac{KT}{q} \tag{4}$$

The leakage current of the diode is expressed by

$$I_0 = I_{rs} \left(\frac{T}{T_n}\right)^3 \exp\left(\frac{qE_{g0}(T_n^{-1} - T^{-1})}{aK}\right) \tag{5}$$

The reverse saturation current I_{rs} is expressed as follows:

$$I_{rs} = \frac{I_{sc}}{\exp\left(\frac{qV_{oc}}{aKT}\right) - 1} \tag{6}$$

The R_p current resistance is expressed as,

$$I_p = \left(\frac{V_{pv} + R_s I_{pv}}{R_p}\right) \tag{7}$$

The characteristic equation can be changed by changing (4) in equations (3) and (7) is expressed as,

$$I_{pv} = I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V_{pv} + R_s I_{pv}}{V_t a}\right) - 1 \right] - \left(\frac{V_{pv} + R_s I_{pv}}{R_p}\right) \tag{8}$$

Figure 2. Equivalent circuit of PV cell.

Figure 1. I-V and P-V Characteristics of model a photovoltaic module under STC (25°C and 1000W/m²).

The curves above represent the current-voltage (I-V) and power-voltage characteristics under Standard Test Condition, where three physical quantities define them:

- V_{oc} : Voltage generated by the unconnected lighted cell
- I_{cc} : Current generated by the lighted cell connected to itself
- MPP (Maximal Power Point): obtained for a maximum voltage and a maximum current, V_{mp} and I_{mp} respectively

With :

- I_{mp} : Optimal operating current
- V_{mp} : Optimal operation voltage
- V_{oc} : Voltage in open circuit
- I_{sc} : Short-circuit current
- I_{pv} : PV cell output current
- V_{pv} : PV cell output voltage
- R_s : Serie resistance of a cell
- R_p : Parallel resistance of a cell
- V_t : Thermal voltage of the module
- T: Working temperature in degrees Kelvin [°K]
- G: Solar irradiation, with $G_0 = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$
- T_n : Nominal or reference temperature (ambient temperature= 298.15 °K)
- E_{g0} : Band gap energy of the semiconductor (1.1 eV)
- q: Electron's charge $e = 1.602 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ C}$
- K: Boltzmann constant ($1.3854 \cdot 10^{-23} \text{ J}^\circ\text{K}^{-1}$)
- k_i : Température coefficient of I_{sc}
- a: Diode quality (or ideality) factor

2. Hot spot defect and detection method

2.1. Hot Spot Fault: Overview

A photovoltaic cell can be equipped with various ohmic shunts whose origin and current-temperature characteristics vary [7]. The one with a local ohmic shunt, the model studied in this paper, can heat up under conditions of shadow, dirt, etc. which, if not detected for a long period of time, generates a hot spot, due to the reverse current through this shunt. The hot-spot fault forms when the internal temperature of a photovoltaic cell rises sufficiently, and causes visible external burns when this hot-spot is not detected quickly [8-9].

However, the cells affected by the hot spot are reverse biased and now act as a load, consuming the energy generated by the other cells. This increases the temperature of the affected cells. As shown in Figure 3a, b, and c [10], fully or partially shaded, cracked, or electrically mismatched photovoltaic cells have a high occurrence rate of hot spot formation, resulting in physical damage (deterioration of the encapsulation material, delamination, cracking, corrosion, interconnect failure, bypass diode failure, mismatch and arcing failure) or by a decrease in the level of electrical output resulting from environmental factors (temporary or permanent shading and fouling). P. Pramana and R. Dalimi [3], note that hot-spot faults account for a percentage of 49% (of which 25% are due to physical damage and 24% due to environmental factors causing diode damage) of the total PV module faults. In addition, hot-spot defects reduce the performance and life cycle of PV systems in general.

Figure 3. Hotspot fault: causes (a) shading, (b) soiling and dust accumulation; (c) hotspot damaged on solar cells.

2.2. Photovoltaic cell in hot spot condition

Kazutaka Itako et al [11], proposed a simple and interesting model of a photovoltaic cell under the effects of the hot spot, represented by a small resistor inserted in its equivalent circuit, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Simplified model of a PV cell in hot spot condition.

However, the resistor R_{IR} consumes a large current I_{IR} , which implies a reduction of the output current I_{pv} of the cell. As a result, the photovoltaic cell is heated due to the temperature increase (hot spot phenomenon), and as long as this phenomenon is not detected, it can cause physical damage in the form of burns, as shown in Figure 7c. Figure 5 shows an internal diagram of the PV module, divided into groups of 10 cells, under different levels of hot spots (from 0% to 100% with an increment of 10%) [12], and whose I-V and P-V curves are given in Figure 6a and b. From these curves, it can be observed that the rate of decrease varies with the rate of occurrence of the hot spot, in other words, the higher the percentage of the hot spot, the more the current drops to a lower photovoltaic voltage compared to other unaffected cells, as shown in Figure 6a. This decrease also implies the reduction of the amount of energy generated by the PV module, as shown in Figure 6b.

Figure 5. Simulation scheme for different levels of hot spots in a PV module.

Figure 6. Characteristic curves for different levels of hot spots: (a) I-V; (b) P-V.

2.3. Hot Spot Detection Method

Traditionally, the detection of hot spot defects is done by infrared/thermal imaging "IMI" which uses infrared cameras (with electromagnetic wavelengths of about 8 to 14um) or thermographic cameras to capture the thermal image of the inspected objects. Generally, photovoltaic cells under the effects of hot spots have a high temperature compared to others not affected. Using the infrared camera, clear differences in color can be observed between these two groups of cells.

The IMI method is considered the most effective and widespread method and uses a non-destructive measurement technique to provide temperature distribution characteristics of the photovoltaic module. It can be used not only for small plants, but also for large PV plants, either by using a crane or forklift, a drone, or by installing sensors integrated in the PV panel for direct measurement of hot spots [13,14]. An example of the causes and effects of hot spot defects, in addition to its visualization by infrared camera, is shown in Figure 7 [10,12]. [15-17] have also proposed, respectively, the technique of hot spot detection using frequency measurement, super-pixel technique SLIC (Simple Linear Iterative Clustering) and the method of gate connection.

Figure 7. (a) Photo of a shaded module under threat of hot spot burn; (b) example of hot spot cells captured by an infrared camera; (c) hot spot related cell damage.

3. I-V characteristic and maximum power point tracking in case of hot spot

3.1. Characteristic in hot spot condition

The I-V data is obtained by I-V scanning of the photovoltaic modules, whose curves have different characteristics depending on the distribution of hot spots. However, the formed curves can be divided into three types namely: hot spot with a distorted curve, hot spot with a single-step curve and a two-step curve, as shown in Figure 8 [8]. The cells affected by the hot spots have a lower short-circuit current than the unaffected ones, so there is a power shift between the two cell types. The I-V curve of the photovoltaic module is then the combination of the curves of all photovoltaic cells, i.e., the I-V curves of the three strings. Furthermore, when the scan point is in the area of high current draw, the affected cell operates in reverse bias and carries a large reverse voltage which, when this voltage reaches a threshold value V_t , the diode in parallel with the string to which the affected cell belongs is activated and the string voltage is limited to a small fixed value of 0.7 V (voltage across the diode); on the other hand, when the scan point is in the region where the current draw is low, the affected cell operates normally, its curve remains the same as that of the unaffected cell and involves a step on that curve, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Various I-V curves of normal PV module and hot spot modules.

It can be seen from Figure 9a that the cell affected by a hot spot has a large slope in the second quadrant, which implies a large reverse leakage current and therefore the slope of the I-V curve at the step is also large until the inflection point of this step disappears and becomes a type of distorted curve. In addition, when the photovoltaic module has two sub-strings affected by hot spots with different short-circuit currents, the two diodes in parallel with the two strings respectively are turned on/off sequentially. However, this change in scan point current sufficiently demonstrates why the I-V curve is two-level, as shown in Figure 9b, where C_1 and C_2 represent the I-V curves of the cells affected by the hot spots in Branch 1 and Branch 2 respectively and P_1 and P_2 represent the on/off points of the diode parallel to Branch 1 and Branch 2 respectively. Furthermore, when there are three strings affected by hot spots, the I-V curve also occurs in two steps, only the overall short-circuit current decreases, due to the series connection between the cells. This phenomenon reduces the production efficiency of the photovoltaic module.

Figure 9. Feature analysis diagram of various types of I-V curves for hot spot modules.

3.2. Maximum power point tracking strategy

Photovoltaic cells have non-linear I-V (current-voltage) and P-V (power-voltage) characteristics such that for a maximum voltage V_m , there is one and only one point (P_m) where they produce maximum power. This point, called the maximum power point (MPP), is subject to deformation in the face of the hot spot fault. Therefore, it is necessary to match the characteristic to a maximum power at each disturbance due to the hot spot. Hence, the maximum power point tracking technique that allows to match or drag the operating point of the photovoltaic cell to the maximum power point and integrated in the photovoltaic system as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Bloc diagram of MPPT photovoltaic system.

Figure 11 shows the characteristics of a photovoltaic cell in MATLAB for different levels of shading, being among the causes of the hot spot fault, for a linear load of resistive type. It can be seen that the maximum power point (MPP) varies according to the level of influence of the shadow leading to different maximum power points which are A' , B' and C' . Since the load is linear, the operating points and corresponding terminal voltages are A , B and C . According to figure 12, the power supplied by the photovoltaic cell with respect to the points A , B and C is clearly lower than the available

power, hence, the maximum power point tracking strategy which allows to maintain the corresponding terminal voltage at the maximum power point A', B' and C', instead of the operating points A, B and C.

Figure 11. I-V and P-V characteristics under different types of shading at T=298 K.

Figure 12. Maximum power point tracking strategy under different types of shading at T=298 K.

4. Conclusion

This work consists of bibliographic research on the performance of photovoltaic modules in the presence of the hot spot fault. It presents the hot spot defect in general, their effects on the characteristic curves and the strategy of monitoring the maximum power point as an undeniable solution to improve the production efficiency of the photovoltaic system. Among the models proposed in the literature, the most common one is the one with a diode in normal and hot-spot conditions. In addition to describing their operating principles, as well as the traditional infrared method used as a detection tool, with a strong focus on the analysis of characteristic curves to assess the production efficiency of photovoltaic systems in the presence of this type of defect. In addition to the previous literatures, small tests on Matlab allow to well identify the adverse effects of the hot spot and to conclude that:

- 1) Photovoltaic systems are extremely sensitive to the hot-spot fault, whose efficiency and maximum power can be completely reduced. This sensitivity can vary depending on the level of hot spots in the photovoltaic module.
- 2) The integration of a maximum power point tracker (MPPT) in the photovoltaic system allows to avoid power losses due to the harmful effects of the hot spot.

The need for MPPT in the photovoltaic system improves the efficiency of solar production and maximizes its power output.

References

- [1] Teo J C, Tan R, Mok V, Ramachandaramurthy V and Tan C 2018 *Impact of Partial Shading on the P-V Characteristics and the Maximum Power of a Photovoltaic String Energies* **11** 1860.
- [2] SolarPowerEurope 2022 *Global Market Outlook for SolarPower 2022-2026*.
- [3] Pramana P A A and Dalimi R 2020 *Hotspot Detection Method in Large Capacity Photovoltaic (PV) Farm Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* **982** 012019.
- [4] Djalab A, Bessous N, Rezaoui M M and Merzouk I 2018 *Study of the Effects of Partial Shading on PV Array IEEE International Conference on Communications and Electrical Engineering (ICCEE)* pp.1-5.
- [5] Metatla A, Talbi N and Benzahiou S 2013 *On the Modelling of Photovoltaic Generators: A Comparative Study IEEE Eighth International Conference and Exhibition on Ecological Vehicles and Renewable Energies (EVER)* pp. 1-5.
- [6] Alam Z, Khan M A, Khan Z A, Ahmad W, Khan I, Khan Q, Irfan M and Nowakowski G 2023 *Fault Diagnosis Strategy for a Standalone Photovoltaic System: A Residual Formation Approach* **12** 282.
- [7] Hans J S, Hallvard G F, Einar A S and Sean E F 2013 *Measurement and Simulation of Hotspots in Solar Cells* **38** pp. 183-189.
- [8] Ma M, Liu H, Zhang Z, Yun P and Liu F 2019. *Rapid Diagnosis of Hot Spot Failure of Crystalline Silicon PV Module Based on I-V Curve*. *Microelectron. Reliab.* Vol. 100-101 113402.
- [9] Schill C, Brachmann S and Koehl M 2015 *Impact of Soiling on IV-Curves and Efficiency of PV-Modules Sol. Energy* vol.112 pp. 259–262.
- [10] Mellit A, Tina G M and Kalogirou S A 2018 *Fault Detection and Diagnosis Methods for Photovoltaic Systems: A Review Elsevier Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* vol.91 pp. 1-17.
- [11] Yang S, Itako K, Kudoh T, Koh K and Ge Q 2018 *Monitoring and Suppression of the Typical Hot-Spot Phenomenon Resulting from Low-Resistance Defects in a PV String IEEE J. Photovolt.* Vol. 8 pp. 1809–17.
- [12] Gosumbonggot J and Fujita G 2019 *Global Maximum Power Point Tracking under Shading Condition and Hotspot Detection Algorithms for Photovoltaic Systems Energies* **12** 882.
- [13] Cubukcu M and Akanalci A, 2020 *Real-time Inspection and Determination Methods of Faults on Photovoltaic Power Systems by Thermal Imaging in Turkey Renew Energy* vol. 147 (Part 1) pp. 1231–38.
- [14] Libra M, Daneček M, Lešetický J, Poulek V, Sedláček J and Beránek V 2019 *Monitoring of Defects of a Photovoltaic Power Plant Using a Drone Energies* vol. 12 795.
- [15] Kim K A, Seo B C G and Krein P T 2016 *Photovoltaic Hot-Spot Detection for Solar Panel Substrings Using AC Parameter Characterization IEEE Trans. Power Electron* **31** pp. 1121–30.
- [16] Alsafasfeh M, Abdel-Qader I, Bazuin B 2017 *Fault detection in photovoltaic system using SLIC and thermal images*. In *Proceedings of the 2017 8th International Conference on Information Technology (ICIT)* pp. 672–676.
- [17] Dong F, Hou M, Feng H, Jin Z, Tian J 2016 *Research on the reconstruction method of PV module based on the door connection*. In *Proceedings of the 2016 IEEE PES Asia-Pacific Power and Energy Engineering Conference (APPEEC)* pp. 337–341.

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